

Tunable Plasmonic Response of Silver Nanoparticles Entangled in Detonation Nanodiamond Network via Colloidal Self-Assembly

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This study explores the self-assembly of nanocomplexes formed by well-defined 20-nm colloidal silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) with 4-nm detonation nanodiamonds (DNDs), focusing on plasmonic resonance. Water-diluted DNDs spontaneously aggregate into chain-like structures entangling AgNPs, forming stable nanocomplexes that sediment within minutes but maintain their plasmonic properties even after redispersion, indicating robust interparticle bonding and interactions. While driven by electrostatics, the binding is stabilized by surface chemistry. AgNPs become spatially entangled yet not aggregated within the DND network, resulting in 8-nm red shift of the plasmonic peak. This nanocomplex morphology is supported by transmission electron microscopy images and electromagnetic numerical simulations. Modeling shows that a 3-nm gap between AgNP and DND particles consistently reproduces experimental data, confirming that DNDs modulate the plasmonic electromagnetic field. Moreover, the plasmonic peaks undergo pronounced intensity changes depending on AgNP concentration: low concentrations enhance (up to +78%), whereas high concentrations lead to suppression (down to -49%) of AgNP plasmonic absorption, independent of DND content. The model shows that, this arises from AgNP field redistribution and interference. The AgNP-DND entangled nanocomplexes thus offer a simple route to a stable hybrid nanoparticle system with tunable optical properties for diverse applications, from biosensing to catalysis, energy conversion or quantum technologies.

1. Introduction

Today, nanoparticles (NPs) play a crucial role in various biomedical and industrial applications, leveraging the unique properties arising from their size. These properties include enhanced reactivity, tunable optical behavior, and the ability to interact with biological systems at a molecular level, utilized in diagnostics, therapeutics, and materials sciences.^[1-3]

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) exhibit a unique set of physical, chemical, and biological properties compared to their bulk counterparts due to their high surface to volume ratio. AgNPs are well known for their strong antimicrobial activity and excellent electrical and thermal conductivity. Their surface can be easily functionalized, allowing for tunability in biomedical, sensing, catalytic applications, or stabilization against aggregation.^[3-5] AgNPs with a size smaller than incident light wavelengths exhibit localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) like other noble metal NPs. The interacting light of a characteristic wavelength induces the oscillation of the free electrons of the particle. The oscillations are coherent and collective, leading to an

enhanced electromagnetic field that gradually decays over time by energy dissipation. The energy of plasmons can be lost in various forms, such as heat, light, charge transfer or even the induction of electric current or enzyme-like activity, depending on factors like particle size.^[5-7] Many parameters, such as particle material, synthesis method, size, shape, and chemical surroundings, influence the specific inducing wavelength and so the whole plasmonic system.^[2-6] Tuning the particle attributes and its environment, the optical properties and decay mechanisms releasing energy can be tailored to serve specific applications. This particle-light interaction is utilized in bioimaging, biosensing, drug delivery, thermotherapy, energy harvesting, and catalysis.^[3,4,6,8-12] Additionally, the combination of AgNPs with other materials can not only alter the plasmonic properties but also significantly impact their stability, conductivity, and biocompatibility.

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Nanodiamonds (NDs) have emerged as promising partners in hybrid nanomaterials due to their physical stability, rich surface functionality, thermal stability, and biocompatibility. The synthesis method, particle size, and surface termination of nanodiamonds strongly affect their chemical and physical properties, colloidal behavior, and interactions with other materials.^[13–15] Combined with plasmonic particles, these systems can exhibit synergistic and multifunctional properties.^[16–20] For instance, nanocomposites of AgNPs with NDs have demonstrated improved antibacterial or photocatalytic activity.^[21–23] And in colloidal mixtures with high-pressure high-temperature nanodiamonds (HPHT NDs), plasmonic absorption of AgNPs has been observed to both increase and decrease depending on particle interactions.^[24] Detonation nanodiamonds (DNDs) synthesized by oxygen-deficient detonation of carbon precursors^[25] exhibit a narrow size distribution ≈ 5 nm^[26,27] and possess surfaces with various functional groups (mostly oxygenated) and/or an amorphous carbon layer.^[25] In aqueous solution, DNDs tend to aggregate into lace-like networks,^[27,28] a distinctive architecture that, rather than being limiting, can be purposefully leveraged in nanocomplex design and reveal novel properties.^[29] Beyond biomedicine,^[25] they are employed in areas such as rheology,^[30] electronics,^[31] and catalysis.^[32]

In this study, we present an investigation aimed at understanding how plasmonic nanoparticles interact with different types of nanodiamond materials. Specifically, we explore self-assembled nanocomplexes of AgNPs and DNDs, focusing on their structure, stability, properties and interparticle interactions. This study expands upon our previous work on plasmonic particles and HPHT nanodiamonds,^[24] and thus, the experimental methodology is deliberately kept consistent with the previous work for straightforward comparison. Experimental results are complemented with electromagnetic numerical simulations and imaging techniques, including optical, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The results reveal effects specific to DNDs due to distinctly different sizes and surface chemistry. Unlike the prior study, DNDs form a nanoscale network with AgNP nodes, where DNDs act as a dielectric mediator modulating the electromagnetic field of plasmonically active AgNPs. These findings reveal a robust AgNP-DND nanocomplex structure with simple, well-controlled formation and tunable plasmonic response, thereby offering a foundation for further development of hybrid plasmonic-diamond systems.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Pristine Colloids

The absorption spectra of pristine colloids are shown in **Figure 1A** for AgNPs and in **Figure 1B** for DNDs, both diluted in HPLC water. AgNP spectra in **Figure 1A** had a characteristic plasmonic peak at 394 nm, the intensity of which depended on AgNP concentration. The spectra showed increased absorption in the UV region, corresponding to increased scattering. A subtle peak starting at 230 nm reflected the AgNP electron interband transition. After the plasmonic peak, the absorption dropped significantly and stayed minimal through Vis and infrared regions. Dilutions below $2.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were excluded from the analysis due to insufficient signal intensity at the absorption peak. AgNP parti-

cles stabilized by sodium citrate showed no signs of instability in their absorption spectra, dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis (mean size of 16 nm, **Figure S1**, Supporting Information), or zeta potential (ZP) analysis (-36 mV), all conducted at $2.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ concentration and pH 7.1. Detonation nanodiamond absorption spectra, **Figure 1B**, showed no distinct features, aside from increased absorption in the UV region, which is attributed to scattering and a bandgap of 5.5 eV.^[33] DND concentrations ranging from 500 to $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were employed, as their absorption was stably detectable in the region of interest (wavelengths of the silver plasmonic peak, i.e., 300–500 nm) and remained below the optical density (OD) of AgNPs. This contrast between AgNPs and DNDs facilitated the analysis of their mixtures, as the DND contribution in the Vis region did not overlap with the prominent AgNP plasmonic peak. Although stable at stock concentration, DNDs began to aggregate once diluted in water. Aggregated detonation nanodiamonds characteristically form distinct chain-like structures and lace-like networks.^[26–28] This aggregation was confirmed by DLS (see **Figure S1**, Supporting Information) and ZP analysis, both summarized in **Figure 1C**. By purpose, no buffer was used to maintain pH, to minimize system complexity and preserve colloid purity. Furthermore, DND aggregation did not correlate with the pH or ZP trends, suggesting that surface chemical group interactions primarily drive the observed behavior.

At the stock concentration ($25\,000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), the DLS analysis reported a mean DND size of 4 nm, consistent with the manufacturer specification. The ZP at this concentration was +33 mV, which generally signifies sufficient colloidal stability. The positive ZP is attributed to the functional groups on the as-received DND surface. The stock solution exhibited an acidic pH of 5.1. Upon water dilution, DLS measurements revealed an increase in the hydrodynamic diameter of the particles, reaching up to 40 nm. Interestingly, the ZP also increased with dilution, rising to approximately +60 mV. Although a higher ZP is associated with improved colloidal stability due to stronger electrostatic repulsion, it is important to note that ZP alone is not the sole determinant of stability. Other factors, such as chemical surroundings, particle size distribution, and temperature, also significantly influence aggregation behavior. Consequently, visible sedimentation occurred within ≈ 20 min after dilution, indicating that ZP measurements were likely performed on pre-aggregated particles. Therefore, the reported ZP values may reflect the electrokinetic potential at the shear plane of these newly formed clusters rather than that of individual nanodiamonds.

2.2. Morphology of Nanocomplexes

Introducing DNDs into AgNP colloid induced spontaneous nanocomplex formation, as demonstrated by optical microscopy, SEM, and TEM images in **Figure 2**. In **Figure 2B**, SEM shows red-marked (by image post-processing) AgNPs particles lying predominantly on the DND structures (grey particles). The absence of AgNP particles outside the DND cluster suggests that the particles were already bound to DND structures before drop-casting, rather than sedimenting during drying. The observed self-assembly was facilitated by the electrostatic attraction between the negatively charged AgNPs and the positively charged

Figure 1. Absorption spectra of pristine colloids of A) AgNPs and B) DNDs diluted by HPLC water. The data curves are averages from triplicate, blank-corrected samples. C) Evolution of DLS size from number distribution (blue), ZP (green) and pH (labels) upon water dilution of DND colloid from stock concentration ($25\,000\ \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to $125\ \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

DNDs. More detailed information about the nanocomplex structure can be derived from the TEM images (Figure 2C,D). AgNP particles are projected by a darker color, because of the higher electron density contrast, with a typical spherical shape and sizes corresponding to information from the manufacturer and DLS analysis. In contrast, DND particles are presented with a lighter color and with sharper edges. The individual size of DND particles was $\approx 4\ \text{nm}$. At higher magnification, TEM images (Figure 2D) revealed that the DND clusters consisted of interconnected chain-like networks with open regions rather than compact agglomerates. These open regions and branched cluster edges acted as trapping sites for AgNPs, leading to efficient self-assembly where most AgNPs became incorporated into the nanocomplexes rather than remaining dispersed in the colloid. This observation demonstrated an effective AgNP-DND nanocomplex self-assembly. The nanocomplexes formed spatially extended, percolated networks rather than compact, densely aggregated structures. This arrangement positioned AgNPs unusually close to one another while still preventing direct contact. In some cases, nanometer-sized gaps were observed between AgNP particles and DND structures. From TEM images alone, however, it remains unclear whether these gaps are imaging artefacts or reflect the presence of a sodium citrate layer surrounding the AgNPs.

Although some isolated DND clusters and free AgNPs were present, nanocomplexes were clearly dominant in the colloidal mixtures. The resulting arrangement of nanocomplexes was irregular in both number and position, with no evidence of a well-ordered assembly. The nanocomplexes displayed a broad size distribution, ranging from a few tens of nanometers to micrometer-sized structures. This observation was consistent with DLS analysis, which indicated a wide size distribution and mean sizes between 1 and $5\ \mu\text{m}$ based on the number-weighted distribution provided in Supporting Information (Figure S1, Supporting Information). With time, sample sedimentation caused the size increase, reaching sizes up to millimeters, accompanied by a rich dark yellow coloration as shown in Figure 2A. Comparison of freshly prepared and aged (30 min) samples showed no morphological changes in the nanocomplexes (see Figure 2D ii,iii).

Although the preparation of SEM and TEM samples by drop-casting may induce structural changes and therefore did not perfectly represent the nanocomplex state in the colloidal form, these imaging techniques remained valuable for revealing the morphology and assembly patterns, which differed from the previous investigation with HPHT NDs. The nanocomplexes with HPHT NDs also formed via self-assembly but tended to exhibit a more tightly aggregated and compact morphology, where multiple AgNPs were located around one bigger central nanodiamond or its

Figure 2. A) Optical microscope, B) SEM, C,D) TEM images of a colloidal mixture of $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ detonation nanodiamonds and $18 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ silver nanoparticles. The image from electron microscopy (A) with $1000\times$ magnification features sediments in the colloidal mixture. The SEM image (B) was obtained by overlapping the background image from the SE signal, capturing the morphology of the nanocomplexes with red-marked areas corresponding to AgNPs based on the BSE signal. The TEM image (C,D i.) of mixtures observed 30 min after preparation, containing black silver nanoparticles and lighter detonation nanodiamonds, (D ii–iv.) of freshly prepared mixtures of silver nanoparticles (dark) and detonation nanodiamonds (light).

compact cluster.^[24] The percolated arrangement observed in Ag-DND complexes may influence the collective optical response of the system and produce specific attributes. To properly perform the spectrophotometric experiments, a further characterization of colloidal behavior and stability was necessary. Thus, we conducted ZP and DLS measurements, discussed in the following section.

2.3. Stability of Nanocomplexes

As described in Section 2.1, DNDs tended to aggregate upon dilution in water, which facilitated nanocomplex formation with AgNPs. As shown in Figure 3A (i), the diluted pristine DND colloid ($125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) appeared transparent without any visible sedimentation. The transparent silver colloid was uniformly yellow and free of sediment, as shown in Figure 3A (ii). Im-

mediately after preparation, their mixture also remained transparent with a yellow hue and no apparent sedimentation, visually indistinguishable from the pristine AgNP colloid (Figure 3A (iii)). However, after ≈ 20 min, large dark yellow flocculates settled at the bottom, suspended in a clear supernatant (Figure 2A (iv,v)). This indicates that the presence of AgNPs intensified the aggregation of the diluted DNDs in the mixture. The supernatant exhibited nearly no plasmonic peak (Figure S2, Supporting Information), suggesting that it was almost devoid of AgNPs, further confirming an effective entanglement of AgNPs by DNDs. Upon mixing, the ZP dropped to negative values close to 0 mV, with the exact value depending on the AgNP concentration, as depicted in Figure 3B. Such pronounced sedimentation was not observed for previously studied nanocomplexes of AgNPs and HPHT NDs, where considerably fewer sediments appeared only after 24 h in the case of mixtures with hydrogenated NDs.^[24]

Figure 3. A) Photos of (ii) pristine AgNPs (18 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), (i) diluted pristine DNDs (125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), and their mixture (iii) right after the preparation, (iv) left to stand for 1 r, (v) and with gently shaken sediments. B) ZP and pH of colloidal mixtures containing 125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs and AgNPs of concentrations depicted on the x-axis. C) photos of samples in the wells (i) before and (ii) after a 1.5-hour spectrophotometry measurement. D) A graph of OD changes of colloidal mixture (125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs and 18 or 2.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs) in time with an OD of pristine silver colloid at time 0. E) Absorption spectra of colloidal mixtures were measured for 1 hour after their preparation, approximately every 4.5 min in triplicate. The black dotted spectra belong to pristine AgNPs of respective concentration, and the black vertical line denotes their plasmonic wavelength.

The sediments could be temporarily redispersed by simple hand agitation but reformed within a few minutes. Notably, neither hand agitation, vortex mixing, nor sonication (up to 10 min) of samples left undisturbed for 1.5 h restored the plasmonic wavelength to that of the pristine AgNPs (see Figure S2, Supporting Information). Figure 3C presents the optical

changes in the mixtures after 1.5 h of spectrophotometry measurements. Over the subsequent 1.5 h, the plasmonic wavelength of both redispersed and unagitated samples remained similar, with only their OD varying due to the sedimentation. Thus, the mechanical forces did not disintegrate the nanocomplexes into individual AgNP and DND particles, indicating a

strong interaction between the components. The visually noticeable redispersion likely resulted from fragmentation of the large DND clusters into smaller aggregates, still consisting of the entrapped AgNP particles. Although electrostatic forces drive the nanocomplex assembly, the mechanically irreversible stability may stem from chemical bonds, possibly between hydroxyl groups and sodium citrates on the surface of DNDs and AgNPs, respectively.

The sedimentation was also manifested in the mixture absorption spectra of $125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs, $18 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $2.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs seen in Figure 3E. The spectra were recorded every 4.5 min, starting immediately after mixing. The most significant change occurred in the region of the AgNP plasmonic peaks, as shown in Figure 3D,E. For the mixture of $18 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs, the plasmonic peak intensity steadily decreased relative to pristine AgNPs, stabilizing after ≈ 1 h. In contrast, the $2.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs mixture peak exhibited an initial increase during the first 22.5 min, followed by a gradual decline, although the OD remained higher than the pristine AgNPs. The trend reflects the nanocomplex formation process: initially, AgNPs and DNDs rapidly form nanocomplexes, leading to an OD increase, which is subsequently reduced over time by sedimentation. In the mixture with $18 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs, only an exponential decay of OD was observed, without clearly distinguishable phases of nanocomplex formation and sedimentation. A red shift of the plasmonic peak was observed in both mixtures, with an initial shift of 4 nm immediately after mixing, increasing to 8 nm by the end of the one-hour experiment.

2.4. Optical Absorption of Nanocomplexes – Plasmonic Peak Wavelength

As described in Figure 3E, the optical absorption spectra of the colloidal mixtures changed, mainly in the plasmonic peak characteristics, compared to the spectra of pristine colloids. We observed variations in the plasmonic peak wavelength and intensity of the nanocomplexes in time. However, it remains unclear whether the presence of DNDs fundamentally altered the plasmonic properties of AgNPs (see Figure 4). Plasmonic resonance manifests in the absorption spectra by a distinct peak defined by its wavelength, intensity, and bandwidth. Variations in any of these parameters can arise from several factors that affect plasmonic resonance, including changes in the surrounding environment, surface chemistry, particle size, and interactions with other particles. To assess potential interactions between AgNPs and DNDs, we investigated the shifts and intensity changes in the plasmonic peaks. The mixture spectra showed an overall increase in OD, along with a consistent 8-nm red shift of the plasmonic peak observed across all samples and concentrations. In contrast, nanocomplexes formed with HPHT NDs did not show any plasmonic peak shifts.^[24] SEM and TEM images (Figure 2) revealed no agglomeration of silver nanoparticles, which appeared either isolated (in small numbers) or entangled within the DND chain-like networks. Although closer together in these networks than in pristine colloids, the particles were not in direct contact. Therefore, the observed 8-nm red shift was not caused by AgNP agglomeration. This conclusion was supported by numerical simulations, which predict that the direct contact of two 20-nm spher-

ical silver nanoparticles would induce a much larger red shift of ≈ 100 nm.^[24]

2.5. Numerical Simulations

To better understand the interaction between silver and detonation nanodiamond particles, we performed electromagnetic numerical simulations of various model geometries shown in Figure 5. The model in Figure 5A represents a single silver particle (20 nm) positioned near a detonation nanodiamond particle (4 nm) coated with an amorphous carbon layer (0.5 nm), reflecting the properties of the DNDs. Their interparticle distance varied from direct contact to a 5-nm gap. In this configuration, we did not observe any changes in the plasmonic peak wavelength. However, the plasmonic energy became slightly localized between the AgNP and DND, disrupting the polarization symmetry of an isolated silver particle.

The plasmonic wavelength red-shifted as more AgNPs surrounded the DND (Figure 5B), depending on the distance between the silver particles and the nanodiamond. The most pronounced shift occurred at direct contact, though wavelength changes were still observed when particles were separated by a gap. For two AgNPs alone, it has been previously computed that a gap larger than 5 nm is sufficient to prevent the plasmonic wavelength shift.^[24] A shift was observed despite such distances between AgNPs in our system, demonstrating that the DND networks modified and redistributed the local electromagnetic fields of AgNPs, causing not only the red shift and increase of absorption with decreasing distance, but also the interaction between the AgNP particles themselves.^[34,35] These promoted AgNP interactions resulted in electromagnetic field interference projected as multiple peaks in the absorption spectrum. Notably, AgNP particles were surrounded by more DND particles, not the other way around, as evident from the SEM/TEM images (Figure 2) and modeled in Figure 5C, where a single AgNP was positioned close to the DND chain. This configuration did not lead to a plasmonic peak shift regardless of distance. By arranging three AgNPs around the DND chain (Figure 5D), the plasmonic peak red shifted and increased in absorption because of the interaction of two AgNP particles^[36] that were not separated by the chain. Their interaction also resulted in multiple peaks, which were not observed experimentally. However, by rotating the model by 90° as seen in Figure 5E, positioning the DND chain perpendicular to electromagnetic polarization, the interference between individual AgNPs decreased. The DND chain guided the electromagnetic fields of AgNPs, bending the plasmonic resonance axis toward the center. For AgNPs with a 15 nm distance or more from the DND chain, the plasmonic wavelength remained stable at 387 nm, indicating that each AgNPs behaved independently without mutual influence. Smaller gaps led to a red shift. The experimentally observed 8 nm red shift corresponded to the model with a 3-nm gap. Since this shift was not observed for the model of the DND chain and a single AgNP, the experimentally observed behavior was attributed to the DND network trapping AgNPs close to each other and mediating their electromagnetic fields.

AgNP-DND system represents a metal-dielectric interface that cannot be described by conventional plasmonic scaling

Figure 4. Absorption spectra of colloidal mixtures (full lines), pristine colloid of silver (dotted lines) and pristine diluted solution of DNDs (black curves). The vertical black line indicates the 394 nm plasmonic wavelength of pristine silver colloid. The data curves are averages from triplicate, blank-corrected samples. Concentrations of silver nanoparticles in the mixture and pristine colloid are denoted in the legend, and concentrations of DNDs corresponding to the mixture and pristine solution are included in the label of the spectra.

laws,^[35–37] as nanodiamonds lack LSPR, and direct plasmonic coupling between these particles cannot happen. Instead, DNDs can alter plasmonic particle surroundings^[6,38] and locally modify their electromagnetic field.^[24] While the actual AgNP-DND gap in real systems may differ from the 3 nm estimated by modeling, the key point is the existence of physical separation. The numerical model is a simplified approximation that neglects variations in particle size, shape, number, and complex geometry. In spite of that, the model correlates very well with experimental observations. Both simulations and experiments support the presence of such a gap as an essential structural feature.

The gap may be attributed to the presence of sodium citrate, used to stabilize AgNP colloids. This molecular layer hinders di-

rect contact between AgNPs and DND particles by maintaining physical separation,^[39] thus preventing the formation of a one-body system in which the components would lose their characteristics and behave as a single plasmonically-coupled entity. The citrate layer might be visible in the TEM images (see Figure 2D) as a light space between particles; however, imaging artefacts cannot be ruled out. The sodium citrate layer width depends on the AgNP synthesis, and it can influence the interactions between plasmonic nanoparticles and their environment.^[39–42] Its role as a spacer in our case should be regarded as a hypothesis based on the absence of major plasmonic shifts, and further work is required to directly probe bonding and interfacial chemistry. In previous work, a 3 nm gap attributed to the sodium citrate layer between HPHT NDs and metal nanoparticles was calculated to

Figure 5. Results of nanocomplex simulations using the COMSOL Multiphysics RF Module. The models consist of 20 nm AgNPs and a non-conductive 4-nm DNDs with a 0.5-nm amorphous carbon layer ($2 \times 10^3 \text{ S m}^{-1}$). The surrounding medium is water. The electromagnetic field intensity map at the distance (or the distance denoted in the model geometry) between the silver particles and the DND and the plasmonic resonance. Distance-dependent absorption spectra of Ag-DND model, with a 0–10 nm gap between silver nanoparticles and DNDs.

produce no plasmonic wavelength shift, in agreement with spectroscopic experiments.^[24]

Some AgNPs were fully surrounded by DNDs in the nanocomplex according to the TEM images (Figure 2D). The plasmonic wavelength of this model (Figure 5F) remained stable, as did the polarity and symmetry of the AgNP field. The DND circle

did not obstruct the electromagnetic field of AgNPs; instead, the field passed through the DND particles, extending its spatial reach, although with reduced intensity compared to isolated AgNPs. The model (Figure 5G) shows how the AgNP electromagnetic field was distributed, not being fully enclosed by the DNDs. While no significant difference in the plasmonic intensity or

Figure 6. Spectral deconvolution of the pristine AgNP and AgDND spectra for comparison of plasmonic peaks. A) The deconvolution steps of the mixture of $4.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs and $125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs for plasmonic peak analysis. Baseline for the spectrum correction was calculated using the asymmetric least squares (AsLS) method. The corrected spectrum was then modelled by the three Gaussian peaks, where the third one represents the plasmonic peak. B) Plasmonic Gaussian peaks to compare the mixtures of $125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs and pristine AgNPs of the corresponding concentration. C) Plasmonic Gaussian peaks to compare the mixtures of various DND concentrations (250 , 125 , $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and $4.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs with the pristine silver colloid of the same concentration. D) Relative gains and losses in plasmonic peak absorption intensity (OD) measured in the colloidal mixtures as a function of AgNP concentration and DNDs concentration (250 , 125 , and $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) in the mixture. The zero line corresponds to the plasmonic peak OD of the pristine AgNP colloids at 394 nm at the respective concentration. The results are complemented by error bars computed from the combined uncertainty of the standard error of the means of triplicates and reconstruction error of deconvolution.

wavelength was observed, the field bent toward the DND cluster and expanded only through the first incomplete DND layer. This once again confirms that DNDs primarily modify the local surroundings of the AgNPs, leading to a local redistribution of their electromagnetic field without inducing a significant plasmonic wavelength shift. Furthermore, TEM images, spectroscopic experiments and numerical simulations suggest that AgNPs do not directly aggregate onto DND surfaces but remain physically separated.

2.6. Optical Absorption of Nanocomplexes – Plasmonic Peak Intensity

As already described in Section 2.3., the intensity of the mixture spectra evolved due to sedimentation. However, the most significant change occurred immediately after preparation, when no visible sedimentation was yet present (Figure 3D), and the absorption change arose from interaction between AgNPs and DND particles. Moreover, the absorption increase was not uniform across the spectrum but predominantly influenced the plasmonic peak. In the absence of particle interactions, the mixture absorption spectra would be expected to represent the sum

of the individual spectra. Instead, the presence of AgNPs promoted DND aggregation, causing significantly higher absorption mainly in the UV region. Thus, direct spectral comparison alone could not unambiguously reveal potential plasmonic interactions.

To compare the plasmonic peaks of the mixtures with those of the respective pristine AgNP colloids, we performed spectral deconvolution, assuming three components – UV scattering, electron interband transitions, and the plasmonic band. The three Gaussian peaks were obtained from baseline-corrected spectra, where the baseline was calculated using the asymmetric least squares method (AsLS). The deconvolution procedure is visualized in Figure 6A. The spectra root mean square reconstruction errors (RMSE) were low, averaging 0.01 OD , with the highest error of 0.02 OD for the sample containing $18 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs and $250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DNDs. For the plasmonic band (at 3rd Gaussian), RMSE were $\approx 0.015 \text{ OD}$, with the highest error again for the highest AgNP concentration. The lowest concentration ($2.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) showed average peak RMSE of 0.006 . These RMSE, combined with standard errors of the means from measured triplicates, are plotted as combined uncertainty in Figure 6D. While the plasmonic wavelength of pristine AgNPs remained unchanged after the deconvolution, the mixture spectra revealed a more

pronounced red shift than expected from the raw data—shifting to 404–406 nm (10–12 nm red-shift) as seen in Figure 6B,C.

Figure 6B compares the deconvoluted spectra of pristine AgNP and the mixtures. By normalizing the mixture peak intensities to the corresponding pristine values, all samples could be compared as shown in Figure 6D. The peak intensity trends depended on AgNPs concentration: at lower AgNP concentrations, DNDs enhanced plasmonic peak intensity, whereas at higher AgNP concentrations, DNDs suppressed it. This trend was consistent across all samples and corresponds to the observations in Figure 3D. There, mixtures containing 18 and 2.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs showed opposite intensity changes immediately after preparation compared to the pristine silver colloids: the higher-concentration mixture exhibited an exponential decrease below the reference, while the lower-concentration mixture showed logarithmic growth followed by a gradual decline due to sedimentation. Therefore, we attribute the first 20 min to nanocomplex formation. As seen in Figure 6D,C, no clear trend emerged concerning DND concentration in the mixture.

The largest enhancement of +78% occurred in the mixture of DNDs at 125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and AgNPs at 2.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, with an average gain of +69% across the AgNP concentration. Mixtures with 4.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs exhibited an average increase of +35% in mixtures, while 9 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNPs in mixtures resulted in a mean decrease of -7%. The strongest suppression of -49% was observed for the mixture of DNDs at 125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and AgNPs at 18 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, with an average suppression of -41%. Additionally, the 2nd Gaussian peak representing the silver electron interband transition increased in the mixtures compared to pristine AgNPs, suggesting further AgNP-DND interactions. Regarding peak half-width, it broadened with increasing AgNP concentration and decreasing DNDs concentration: averages were +42%, +24%, and +6% for mixtures with 18, 9, and 4.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNP, respectively, while 2.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNP mixtures showed a slight decrease of -0.5%. Consequently, the plasmonic peak area varied from a 68% increase (2.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNP mixtures) to a -17% decrease (18 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ AgNP mixtures).

Thus, the influence of DNDs on the AgNP plasmonic peak can be either enhancing or suppressing, depending on the AgNP concentration, while maintaining the wavelength shift. The numerical simulation showed the importance of the nanocomplex spatial configuration in the AgNP electromagnetic field. A structure with a lower number of AgNP particles reduced lossy AgNP interactions while using the proximity with DND to enhance the local field. The surrounding DNDs can localize and extend the reach of the plasmonic field, thereby amplifying the global plasmonic response (Figure 5E-G). Although the peak intensity increase reflected a stronger plasmonic response, the half-width remained fairly the same, indicating minimal energy loss or preserved oscillation coherence. The peak area increase suggested that AgNPs in the presence of DNDs absorbed more energy than the pristine AgNPs of the same concentration, likely due to enhanced electromagnetic interactions or changes in the local dielectric environment. Since the mixture peak red shift was just a few nanometers (<12 nm), the absorbed light still retained relatively high photon energy.

The suppressing effect of DNDs on plasmonic absorption at higher AgNPs concentrations indicated weaker collective oscillations of free electrons. The simultaneous half-width increase

showed lower coherence of plasmonic oscillations and greater damping. Decreased plasmonic peak area confirmed a loss of absorbed energy. Thus, the plasmonic activity not only changed in terms of quality but also quantity. The intensity decrease can be caused by mutual destructive interference of AgNPs due to the phase shift of oscillations arising from the proximity of AgNPs to each other and their field interactions yet still separated by DNDs without forming a one-body system. In such a configuration, their resonance was asynchronous, and the internal energy loss further decreased coherence and promoted the phase shift.

A similar concentration-dependent trend has been described in nanocomplexes formed in colloidal mixtures of 50-nm surface-modified (hydrogenated or oxidized) HPHT NDs and 20 nm noble metal nanoparticles (silver or gold).^[24] In those systems, the plasmonic peak wavelength remained stable, yet the plasmonic peak intensity increased at lower metal NP concentrations and decreased at higher concentrations – mirroring our observations. These intensity changes were attributed to two opposing interactions between the plasmonic nanoparticles and HPHT NDs acting simultaneously. The enhancement was promoted due to the local charge redistribution at the interface between the metal NPs and the HPHT NDs, facilitated by their proximity. The suppression was attributed to destructive plasmonic interference arising from metal NPs in near-contact. Our findings suggested that the same mechanisms likely operated in the AgNP-DND nanocomplexes. However, the entanglement of 20-nm AgNP within the network of much smaller 4-nm DND afforded greater flexibility in spatial arrangement, allowing stronger modulation of plasmonic effects. While the enhancements observed here were more moderate compared to previous work with HPHT NDs, where increases reached up to +134% without any plasmonic peak shifts, the AgNP-DND system still exhibited pronounced plasmonic enhancements and suppressions, clear plasmonic peak shifts, and distinctive electromagnetic field changes, as also calculated from theoretical electromagnetic models.

3. Conclusion

This study investigated the formation and plasmonic properties of nanocomplexes in colloidal mixtures of AgNPs and DNDs. Unlike HPHT nanodiamonds, which remained more dispersed in aqueous solutions and formed rigid compact nanocomplexes with AgNPs,^[24] DNDs aggregated into lace-like structures that entangled AgNPs and thereby led to the formation of functional nanocomplexes. Due to this feature, DND lace-like network enriched with AgNPs sedimented within minutes, but redispersion did not alter their plasmonic properties, indicating strong bonding likely driven by surface interactions that go beyond simple electrostatics. Whereas the presence of AgNPs markedly accelerated the DND aggregation, no such direct effect was observed for HPHT NDs. The AgNP particles entangled within the DND network were localized closer together than in the pristine colloid, although they were not in direct contact, as evidenced by 8 nm plasmonic red shift and supported by TEM images, which ruled out the AgNP aggregation. The numerical simulations demonstrated that DNDs dielectrically modulated the electromagnetic field of entangled AgNPs, assuming a physical gap of 3 nm between the particles that facilitated the field redistribution across the DND network. Although HPHT NDs were also merged close

together with AgNPs, their interactions did not result in plasmonic wavelength shifts.^[24] Spectral deconvolution revealed that mixtures of DNDs with lower AgNP concentrations resulted in plasmonic peak enhancements of up to +78%, whereas higher AgNP concentrations led to suppression down to -49%, with no clear correlation to DND concentration. The enhancement was attributed to local charge redistribution mediated by DNDs, while the suppression was the result of destructive interference among closely spaced AgNPs separated by DNDs. The same type of interactions was previously identified in the HPHT NDs nanocomplexes. The present study with DNDs thus confirms that such an effect is more general, yet with some differences. Contrary to the previous work, where larger HPHT nanodiamonds showed no plasmonic peak shifts and higher overall enhancement up to +134%, the AgNP-DND system exhibits more pronounced plasmonic peak shifts and local electromagnetic field modulation. It can be attributed to the smaller size, diverse surface functionalities, and more flexible spatial arrangement of DNDs.

This simple, self-assembling system produces stable nanostructures with localized enhanced electromagnetic hotspots, making it promising for applications in nanophotonics and light-matter interactions. This study complements many applications of plasmonic particles with nanodiamonds that have been studied in recent years and can provide useful additional insight for controlling and understanding their properties.

4. Experimental Section

Materials—Detonation Nanodiamonds: NanoAmando Aqueous Colloid Solution (NanoCarbon Research Institute, Ltd.) containing 4 nm elementary particles of DNDs was employed. DNDs were argon-purged and stored in a dark place at a stock concentration of 25 mg mL⁻¹.

Materials—Silver Nanoparticles: Spherical AgNPs in a colloidal form (730793, Sigma) were employed and analyzed at a concentration of 20 µg mL⁻¹ and an average particle size of 20 nm, stabilized by sodium citrate. The colloidal solution was refrigerated at 4 °C and protected from light.

Materials—Colloidal Mixtures: A three-step, two-fold dilution series of AgNPs was performed using HPLC water (Roth), resulting in solutions with concentrations of 20, 10, 5, and 2.5 µg mL⁻¹. A one-step, five-fold dilution of the DND stock solution, initially at a concentration of 25 mg mL⁻¹, was performed, yielded a 5000 µg mL⁻¹ solution. This was followed by two-step two-fold dilution, producing solutions with concentrations of 2500 and 1250 µg mL⁻¹. A final one-step, ten-fold dilution was conducted to obtain a concentration of 125 µg mL⁻¹. Each of these four DND dilutions was mixed with AgNP dilutions in a 1:9 ratio. Each mixture of 500, 250, 125, and 12.5 µg mL⁻¹ DNDs contained four different concentrations of AgNPs: 18, 9, 4.5, and 2.25 µg mL⁻¹. The mixtures were agitated by hand. If sedimentation was wanted, the mixtures were left in a dark place at room temperature.

Methods—UV-vis Spectroscopy: UV-vis spectroscopy was performed using the Epoch2 microplate reader (BioTek) equipped with a xenon lamp and a monochromator with wavelength selection from 200 to 900 nm with a 2 nm increment. Samples were analyzed in triplicate employing a 96-well UV black body microplate without a lid. Measurements were conducted at 37 °C, starting with a 10-s double orbital shake at 282 cycles per minute. Pristine of AgNP and DND colloids at corresponding concentrations were measured as reference samples. HPLC-grade water served as a blank sample. For each experiment, a new set of samples was prepared. Colloidal stability was monitored every 4.5 min per triplicate over at least 1 h, starting immediately after mixing and initial hand shaking or after a sedimentation period. Absorption spectra were processed using MATLAB software (MathWorks, R2023a).^[43]

Methods—Dynamic Light Scattering, Zeta Potential, and pH: DLS and ZP were conducted by Zetasizer Nano (Malvern Panalytical) equipped with a helium-neon laser (633 nm) and scattering angle of 173°. Samples were analyzed in a disposable folded capillary cell with electrodes and allowed to stabilize for 1 min prior to measurement. Measurement reliability was confirmed through the Zetasizer's quality report. All measurements were performed in triplicate. To complement ZP measurements, sample pH was determined at room temperature using the Malvern MPT-2 Multipurpose Autotitrator.

Methods—Redispersion: Hand agitation was performed for 3 min by flipping the Eppendorf tube containing the sample upside down once every second. Mechanical agitation was also carried out using a vortex mixer (ZX3 Advanced Vortex Mixer, VELP Scientifica) for 3 min at 1200 rpm in touch mode. Sonification treatment was applied using an ultrasound bath (Bandelin, Sonorex Digitec DT 31 Ultrasonic Bath) operating at 35 kHz for either 3 or 10 min.

Methods—Scanning Electron Microscopy: SEM was carried out using the Zeiss EVO 10 system operated at an acceleration voltage of 17 kV, a probe current of 5 pA, and a working distance of ≈ 8.5 mm. Samples were prepared by drop-casting onto a silicon wafer substrate and air-dried at room temperature. SEM images were obtained simultaneously using back-scattered electrons (BSE) and secondary electrons (SE) detectors. To visualize the complexes, a mask was generated using the BSE signal through thresholding, differentiating AgNPs from DNDs. The mask was colored red and superimposed onto the SE image using Gwyddion and MATLAB (MathWorks, R2023a).^[43,44]

Methods—Transmission Electron Microscopy: TEM was conducted using the Tecnai G2 20 (FEI) TEM equipped with a LaB6 cathode, operating at 200 kV acceleration voltage, and images were captured using an Olympus Veleta CCD camera. For sample preparation, a carbon-coated copper grid (SPI Supplies) was dipped in the colloidal mixture and allowed to dry prior to imaging.

Methods—Optical Microscopy: Optical microscopy provided images of sedimented nanocomplex clusters in the colloidal mixtures. The microscope (Levenhuk Zoom&Joy) was equipped with a Microscope Color Digital Camera Levenhuk C510 NG. Samples were observed using a 100× oil immersion objective and a standard 10× eyepiece, providing a total magnification of 1000×. Immersion oil was poured between the objective and the cover glass. The TouPView software for imaging was used.

Methods—Numerical Simulations: COMSOL Multiphysics RF Module was employed to model the geometry of AgNP-DND nanocomplexes and simulate their interactions with an incident electromagnetic field. Spherical diamond particles were designed with a 4 nm diamond core and a 0.5 nm thick amorphous carbon shell layer. The properties of the diamond material were assigned using standard bulk values.^[45] While the diamond was non-conductive, the amorphous layer was characterized by a conductivity of 2×10^3 S m⁻¹. Silver spherical particles (AgNPs) with a diameter of 20 nm were placed 0–40 nm apart to analyze their electromagnetic field interference. The dielectric properties of silver were defined according to the Johnsons and Christy empirical model.^[46] The particle properties are summarized in **Table 1**. The distance between the AgNPs and the DND chain varied in a range of 0–20 nm (with a difference of 1 nm for each simulation) to analyze the plasmonic effects. A background electric field of 1 V m⁻¹ was applied. Perfectly matched layers (PML), sized at five times the nanoparticle diameter, were used to minimize reflections from the boundaries and to absorb outgoing waves. Maxwell's equations for the models were solved using the finite element method (FEM). An extra-fine mesh was implemented to ensure accurate analysis of the electric field around the nanoparticles.

Methods—Spectral Deconvolution: A spectral deconvolution was performed using a custom MATLAB script. Spectral baselines were obtained using the asymmetric least squares (AsLS) method, which iteratively adjusts a smooth background estimate by minimizing a penalized least squares function with asymmetry and smoothness constraints ($\lambda = 1e5$, $p = 0.01$, 1000 iterations). The corrected spectra were deconvoluted via nonlinear least-squares fitting of three-component Gaussian models using the MATLAB fit function. This model features three primary spectral peaks with estimated initial parameters (amplitude, wavelength, and

Table 1. Properties provided to particles for numerical simulations.

Material	Properties			
	Diameter [nm]	Relative permeability	Relative Permittivity	Electrical Conductivity [S/m]
AgNPs	20	1	$\epsilon_1 = 15.736$ (Real Part) $\epsilon_2 = 0.028734$ (Imaginary)	0
NDs	4	1	5.7760	0
Amorphous Carbon	0.5	1	$\epsilon_1 = 3.0276$ (Real Part) $\epsilon_2 = 0.010472$ (Imaginary)	2×10^3

standard deviation): UV scattering (4 OD, 180 nm, 50 nm), electron interband transition (1 OD, 225 nm, 50 nm), and the surface plasmon resonance (3 OD, 400 nm, 100 nm). From the fitted models, the parameters of the third peak, attributed to plasmonic absorption – amplitude, wavelength, and width, were extracted. The half-width was computed as FWHM = 2.3548 × standard deviation, and the peak area was determined from the integral of the Gaussian function. Reconstructive error analysis was performed using the root mean square error of the residuals to evaluate the accuracy of the deconvolution fit. The standard deviation from the triplicates was also calculated and combined with the reconstructive errors at the plasmonic peak to estimate the combined uncertainty.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

V.H. performed methodology, visualization, investigation, formal analysis, data curation, wrote the original draft. M.Š.B. performed software, project administration, investigation, formal analysis, wrote reviewed and edited the final manuscript. M.Q. performed methodology, investigation, formal analysis. K.K. performed investigation. B.R. performed supervision, resources, project administration, investigation, formal analysis, conceptualization, acquired funding acquisition, wrote reviewed and edited the final manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15394120>, reference number 15394120.

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colloidal chemistry, detonation nanodiamonds, plasmonic resonance, self-assembled nanocomplexes, silver nanoparticles

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